

The NERC Earth Observation Data Centre

Current and forthcoming data holdings

Steve Donegan

NERC Earth Observation Data Centre

- **Introduction**
- **NEODC Background**
- **Current data holdings**
- **Forthcoming data**
- **Accessing NEODC data**
- **Future developments**

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NATURAL
ENVIRONMENT
RESEARCH COUNCIL

Background

- **The NEODC is 1 of 8 NERC designated data centres**
- **We deal with terrestrial EO data**
- **Satellite or Airborne**
- **Located at CCLRC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, Oxfordshire**
- **Merged management and infrastructure functions with the BADC, also at RAL**

Background

- **Management of EO data acquired with NERC money**
- **Provision of access to data**
- **Development of metadata & website**
- **Purchasing of new EO data**
- **Helpdesk**

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ARSF Data

- **Archive of ARSF data from 1984+**
- **Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) 1984 to date**
- **Compact Airborne Spectrographic Imager (CASI) 1995 to date**
- **LiDAR terrain model data**

SHAC 2000 data

NextMap Britain

- **Airborne radar derived digital terrain dataset**
- **Recently purchased by BGS for NERC**
- **Covers England, Wales and some of Scotland (remainder to follow)**
- **Ground resolution upto 2.5m (depending on mode)**
- **Various modes to choose from: ORI, DSM, DTM etc**
- **Licensed for use by all NERC staff and award holders**

NextMap Britain

Images from <http://istore.intermaptechnologies.com/handbook.cfm>

NextMap Britain

**Ordnance Survey
Landform PROFILE**

**NextMap Britain
SK64 DTM 5m cell**

**NextMap Britain
SK64 DSM**

Courtesy of Nextmap Britain

Combining NextMap DTM and ARSF data

Radiometrically corrected level 1b ATM/CASI data. Post -1992, scan line altitude and location data also recorded.

NextMap Britain DTM of the Tamar estuary

Level 3, geometrically corrected flight line, shown in true-colour. The curvature of the image edges is due to pitch and roll of the platform. Use AZ software suite to do this correction and to extract required bands etc

Combining NextMap DTM and ARSF data

Data from ATM and CASI can be draped over the 3d NextMap DTM data.

Aerial Photography

- **Aerial photography also obtained on many ATM/CASI flights**
- **Wild RC-10**
- **Stereo imaging capability**
- **Negatives held at BGS, Keyworth**

Location of NERC ARSF aerial photographs

Satellite Data

- **Wide selection of Landsat scenes, 1970's to present**
- **SPOT**
- **ERS-1/2 SAR**
- **Ikonos**

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ATSR UBT Archive

- **UBT: Ungridded Brightness Temperature**
- **ATSR2 UBT data will soon be available online**
- **UBT product includes pixel coordinates in latitude and longitude**
- **All other ATSR data products can be derived from the UBT product**
- **ATSR has 7 channels spanning the visible, VNIR, SWIR and TIR**

**Nadir view
Visible/VNIR**

**Forward View
Visible/VNIR**

**Nadir view
11µm channel**

**Forward View
11µm channel**

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Accessing the NEODC archive

- **Web interface –main point of access**
- **Can order data found on the interface**
- **Can download data from webpage or via ftp**
- **Not all data holdings can currently be found on the web interface**
- **Merging user database with that of the BADC**
- **New helpdesk software for more efficient query tracking**
- **Helpdesk: neodc@rl.ac.uk 01235 778123**

Accessing the NEODC archive

NERC Earth Observation Data Centre - Microsoft Internet Explorer provided by ...

Address: <http://www.neodc.rl.ac.uk/index.php>

NERC Earth Observation Data Centre
Featuring the best of NERC Science and Survey with Earth Observation Data and Information

Information: About the NEODC, News items, EO links, NERC, BNSC, International agencies

Data: Airborne, Satellite, Find EO data

Help: Self-help tutorials, FAQ, Documentation, Contact us

Events: EO Spring School

Powered by **membo** Site Server

NERC Earth Observation Data Centre - Microsoft Internet Explorer provided by ...

Address: <http://www.neodc.rl.ac.uk/index.php?option=displaypage&Itemid=93&op=page&SubMenu=80>

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Find Earth Observation data

Start here to look for Earth Observation data to suit your needs. Here are some useful catalogues to get you started:

- Search for individual data items at the NEODC (New XML catalogues)
- New XML-based catalogues, including some LANDSAT data from 1995-2001 and AVHRR data. Note that this new catalogue does not currently contain all items and is still under development. [Click here](#)
- Search for individual data items at the NEODC (old catalogues)
- Locate the data you need by applying detailed search criteria and viewing preview images of individual data items (e.g. a specific LANDSAT scene or AVHRR image). [Click here](#)
- Search for collections of data held at the NEODC
- View descriptions of the datasets held here at the NEODC. These give an overview of the content, purpose, temporal and spatial extent of the data, along with details of access or usage restrictions that may apply. [Click here](#)

NERC Metadata Gateway

Use this wider search to find out about datasets held at the NERC Designated Data Centres and other organisations. [Click here](#)

EDC Geospatial Data Clearinghouse

A portal giving open-access to a huge range of spatial-reference data. Visit the EDC site here. [Click here](#)

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Web development by **membo**

Search the new NEODC metadata catalogue - Microsoft Internet Explorer

Address: <http://www.neodc.rl.ac.uk/databasesearch/newcat/index.php>

Search new NEODC metadata catalogue

This new XML-based metadata catalogue currently contains records for all ATM and CASI data from 1995 onwards, and a limited selection of satellite data, for test purposes. Not all items held by the NEODC are yet included in this catalogue, as it is still under development. Please contact custhelp@neodc.rl.ac.uk if you cannot find what you are looking for.

Restrict your search to a geographic area

Select from map or Select a location

Your selection from one of the tools above should override the values in the boxes below. Alternatively, you can simply type in the lat/lon values defining the bounding rectangle of your search. Use decimal degrees, with north and east positive.

90.0 North
180.0 West 180.0 East
90.0 South

Select records whose the spatial bounding coordinates of the data...
[Are fully enclosed by the region defined above](#)

Restrict your search to a range of dates

from 01 01 1972
to 24 08 2004

Use text search terms

Search for word(s) in field Anywhere

Number of results per page: 10
Summary result display: With images

Submit Query

Select region from map - Microsoft Internet Explorer

Select region from map - Microsoft Internet Explorer

Click and drag to select a geographic bounding rectangle defining your area:

90.0 N
180.0 W 180.0 E
90.0 S
Zoom In Zoom Out

Map world
Preset Locations

Continue

Uses LiveMap_v3.0 map applet.

Accessing the NEODC archive

Search Results - Microsoft Internet Explorer provided by SSTD Office ...

Address: http://www.neodc.rl.ac.uk/datasearch/newcat/zquerybuilder.php?use_latlon=on&nrort

Search Results

Your search term was @attrset geo-attset @and @attr 1=2060 @attr 2=9 @attr 4=201 "90.0 -180.0 -90.0 180.0" @attr 1=1016 @attr 2=3 @attr 4=6 "atm"

Found 2214 matching item(s).

New Query >> View your basket: Empty

#	View...	Summary	Basket
1	View Plain XML	NEODC data item: Tape: AT0682 Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) Flight line File: a267141b.hdf Date: 19970924-19970924 Time: 112909-113216 Originator: NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Facility Location: N: 54.8424 S: 54.7791 W: -4.0779 E: -4.0755 kirkcudbright Bay	
2	View Plain XML	NEODC data item: Tape: AT0683 Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) Flight line File: a267171b.hdf Date: 19970924-19970924 Time: 114210-114648 Originator: NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Facility Location: N: 54.8271 S: 54.7985 W: -4.0789 E: -4.0783 kirkcudbright Bay	
3	View Plain XML	NEODC data item: Tape: AT0784 Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) Flight line File: a301071b.hdf Date: 19951028-19951028 Time: 102300-102529 Originator: NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Facility Location: N: 52.5462 S: 52.5459 W: -2.9133 E: -2.784 Wroxeter	
4	View Plain XML	NEODC data item: Tape: AT0873 Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) Flight line File: a297071b.hdf Date: 19961023-19961023 Time: 104300-104600 Originator: NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Facility Location: N: 52.7523 S: 52.7102 W: -2.5727 E: -2.5711 Wroxeter	

Local intranet

NEODC metadata record - Microsoft Internet Explorer ...

Address: <http://www.neodc.rl.ac.uk/datasearch/newcat/itemwindow.php?>

Summary Location More details General info Access Details Metadata info

NEODC data item: Tape: AT0682 Airborne Thematic Mapper (ATM) Flight line File: a267141b.hdf

Preview Image

Summary Data

Start date	19970924
Start time	112909
End date	19970924
End time	113216
Originator	NERC Airborne Remote Sensing Facility

Earth Cover/ Land Use
Environment
Geoscientific information
Imagery

Done

NEODC metadata record - Microsoft Internet Explorer ...

Address: <http://www.neodc.rl.ac.uk/datasearch/newcat/itemwindow.php?>

Summary Location More details General info Access Details Metadata info

Supplemental information

NEODC Mission and site details from flight logs

NEoproj: steint 1.10 Oct 16 1998

NEoproj2:

NEicopyw: Data: (c) UK Natural Environment Research Council, 1998

NEairc: G-NERC

NEpilot: G. Wightman

NEaviag: J. Cook

NEoper: G. Osborn

NEbase: Coventry

NEdates: 24/9/97

NEfltaa: 089

NEproico:

NEploff: A. M. Folkard, University of Strathclyde/Civil Engineering

Theme Keywords

GCMD Science Keywords

http://gcmd.gsfc.nasa.gov/Resources/valids/gcmd_parameters.html

EARTH SCIENCE>Land Surface>Land Use/Land Cover>Land Use Classes

EARTH SCIENCE>Land Surface>Landscape>Landscape Pattern

EARTH SCIENCE>Land Surface>Surface Radiative Properties>Reflectance

EARTH SCIENCE>Land Surface>Topography>Landforms

EARTH SCIENCE>Radiance Or Imagery>Infrared Wavelengths>Brightness Temperature

EARTH SCIENCE>Radiance Or Imagery>Infrared Wavelengths>Infrared Fluz

EARTH SCIENCE>Radiance Or Imagery>Visible Wavelengths>Visible Imagery

EARTH SCIENCE>Radiance Or Imagery>Visible Wavelengths>Visible Imagery

NERC AIRS scene categorisation

Estuary

GIGateway theme keywords <http://www.gigateway.co.uk>

Earth Cover/ Land Use
Environment
Geoscientific information
Imagery

GIGateway theme keywords <http://www.gigateway.co.uk>

Earth Cover/ Land Use
Environment
Geoscientific information
Imagery

Done

Local intranet

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Future developments

- **Addition of (A)ATSR UBT data will result in a continuous, consolidated archive**
- **Continuing to create a full Metadata catalogue of all NEODC data holdings**
- **NEODC is actively involved in development of new ways for accessing EO data**
- **Closer collaboration with BADC, with the goal of making EO data available via the NERC datagrid**

MASS ATSR2 GeoTiff service

SSE Portal - Microsoft Internet Explorer provided by SST Office Systems

Address: <https://services.eoportal.org/portal/Portal-homePage.jsp>

Service Support Environment

User: SteveDonegan | Order List | Profile | Log out

Services
The SSE service directory offers access to a continuously expanding set of basic and complex Earth observation and GIS services. You can request a quotation for each of the services or order them via an online form. To order paying services, you should be a registered SSE user.

Products
Search and browse through the available catalogues to find the proper product to use as input for your SSE service. You may as well order the earth observation products for your own further processing.

Organisations
The SSE portal will give access to a large variety of services from a diverse set of contributors such as; space agencies, data processing centres, data providers, educational establishments, private companies and research centres.

News
User registration is free of charge. As a registered SSE user, you can subscribe to receive earth observation news by email, or consult the latest news on the Portal. You can specify what category of news you are interested in.

About us
The current SSE environment was originally developed in the framework of the GSTP programme for ESRIN by a Consortium consisting of SPACEBEL, Intecs, Telespazio, Kongsberg Spaceteq, GIM and VITO and will be operated by the European Space Agency ESRIN in Frascati (Italy).

Search:

Quick Links: Organisations, Documents, Services, Software, News, Discussion forum, Contact Us

SSE Portal - Service Directory - Microsoft Internet Explorer provided by SST...

Address: <http://services.eoportal.org/portal/service/ListService.do?serviceCategoryId=sub21>

Service Support Environment

User: SteveDonegan | Order List | Profile | Log out

Resources of Satellite Image Processing

Catalogue	(European Space Agency)	This service allows to perform searches across various image catalogues....	<input type="button" value="Proceed"/>
ESA ATSR service supported by NEODC/RAL	(European Space Agency)	ESA and UK agencies are preparing a new service, starting mid-2005, to provide easy access to all	<input type="button" value="Proceed"/>
NRT MERIS	(GAEI Consultant)	NRT MERIS...	
S10 Basic	(VITO)	Synthesis products are corrected atmospherically (values corresponding to surface reflectances). S10 products are obtained from...	
Test Product Order	(European Space Agency)	This is a demo service for product ordering....	<input type="button" value="Proceed"/>

Directory of Data provision services

Navigate to subcategory

- Data Conversion
- Satellite Image Processing

About | Search | Contact Us

MASS ATSR2 GeoTiff service

SSE Portal - Search Process - Microsoft Internet Explorer provided by SSTD Office Sy...

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Back Forward Stop Home Search Favorites Media

Links J2SE Java 2 Platform UBT Progress NEODC Axis API FOOTPRINTS NERC QMASS

Address http://services.eoportal.org/portal/order/PrepareOperation.do?serviceId=AC808980&operation=Search

Service Support Environment

User: SteveDonegan Order List Profile Log out

ESA ATSR service supported by NEODC/RAL Search

Map Box

Use the buttons above the map to zoom in and define your AOI

Date: From: 2004 Sep 06 To: 2004 Sep 06

Retrieve: 10 metadata

Starting from: 1

@ www.demris.nl

Scale: 10000 km

Search Next

x:153.161954,y:-110.591260

SSE Portal - Search Process - Microsoft Internet Explorer provided by SSTD Office Sy...

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

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Links J2SE Java 2 Platform UBT Progress NEODC Axis API FOOTPRINTS NERC QMASS

Address http://services.eoportal.org/portal/order/PrepareOperation.do?serviceId=AC808980&operation=Search

Service Support Environment

User: SteveDonegan Order List Profile Log out

ESA ATSR service supported by NEODC/RAL Search

Map Box

Use the buttons above the map to zoom in and define your AOI

Date: From: 1995 Sep 06 To: 1995 Sep 10

Retrieve: 10 metadata

Starting from: 1

@ www.demris.nl

Scale: 10000 km

Search Next

Product Identifier	Collection	Platform	Acquisition Date/Time	Satellite Domain	Graphical Overview
ralubt-9509060922-13111	ESA.ERS.ATSR.UBT	ERS-2	1995-09-06T09:54:54.404		
ralubt-9509082003-06329	ESA.ERS.ATSR.UBT	ERS-2	1995-09-08T20:18:54.764		

x:169.820051,y:-69.871465

MASS ATSR2 GeoTiff service

Present Results - Microsoft Internet Explorer provi...

Administrative information		Technical characteristics	
Organisation Name:	NEODC	Mission:	ERS-2
Organisation Role:	custodian	Sensor:	ATSR-2
Product Identifier:	ralubt-9509060922-13111	Sensor mode:	Not available
Abstract:	Not available	Orbit:	2
Product Status:	completed	Orbit direction:	ascending
Geographic location		Last Orbit:	2
Polygon Coordinates:	55.25,28.370001 61.152,28.370001 61.152,17.110001 55.25,17.110001	Frame:	2
Temporal information		Track:	2
Start Date:	1995-09-06T09:54:54.404	Swath:	Not available
End Date:	1995-09-06T09:56:11.052	III. Elevation Angle:	90.0
Metadata Date:	1967-08-13	III. Azimuth Angle:	360.0
		Cloud Coverage Percentage:	100.0
		Not available:	Not available

ralubt-9509060922-13111-031113-2v350.ubt-tvl (N A D I R)

SSE Portal - Order Preparation - Microsoft Internet Explorer provided by SSTD Of...

Service Support Environment

User: SteveDonegan Order List Profile Log out

ESA ATSR service supported by NEODC/RAL Order

Project Description:
Test ATSR2 UBT
GeoTiff download

Output Option:
geotiff

View:
nadir

Channel:
B370

Selected Product:
ralubt-9509060922-13111

Order Identifier: AE809880
Price: 0.5 EUR

Please check your order information.
You can continue ordering the selected service by selecting the Proceed button.

Proceed Reset

About Search Contact Us

x:-41.239892,y:117.897574

